

"Developing Book Culture among Elementary School Students and Fostering its Cultural Technology"

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Annotation: This article discusses the promotion of book culture among elementary school students, the development of book culture, and the technology that can make reading more appealing.

Key words: librarianship, "Reading culture," "Book culture," interest, internet, journals.

Throughout our history, the issue of librarianship has evolved in various ways during different periods. Each era has defined its own level of library development. Notably, the strength of any state is often determined by the intellectual capacity of its scholars. In this regard, due attention has always been given to the issue of librarianship. In today's society, concepts such as "Cultural literacy," "Library culture," and "Reading culture" are commonly used to describe the social phenomena associated with the acquisition of information. While the word "literacy" traditionally refers to "reading," today it encompasses a much broader understanding beyond reading books. According to A. Umarov, "Cultural literacy" is the sum of knowledge, skills, and activities that are aimed at obtaining general information, values, and events through the means of social groups, associations, and individual activities, as well as various attributes. At the same time, cultural literacy does not form special formations through educational systems. It presents a set of changes in various forms throughout one's life - books (fiction, scientific, educational, entertaining), mass media (newspapers, journals, television, radio, and the like), modern information technologies (the internet, electronic newspapers, journals, and directories), as well as people who transmit knowledge in different ways (family members, teachers, etc.). Therefore, it is necessary to differentiate general information obtained in various forms and ways from the subject with the means of communication with it. Professor E.I. Yoldoshev defines "Reading culture" as follows: "Reading culture is very multifaceted and includes being interested in books, becoming familiar with literature, gaining specialized knowledge about books and working with them, as well as acquiring the necessary skills to use books efficiently, including reading to the end."

"Education encompasses teaching, learning, and developmental processes. It plays a significant role in cultivating the culture of acquiring information. Knowledge acquired equips students to explore further. The content of the educational process is not confined to classroom lessons that only include subject matter, concepts, and skills. Instead, it extends beyond the classroom into extracurricular activities and independent engagement within information-rich environments such as libraries.

Librarianship, in particular, organizes information about the basic methods of obtaining and working with it. Librarianship courses lay the foundation for this. In these courses, working with information, getting acquainted with books, reading books critically, and developing organizing skills are essential. Additionally, utilizing electronic libraries, electronic catalogs, and information databases is taught to harness their potential fully.

However, this is not an isolated process, but rather, it should be an integral part of the educational system.

Today, Uzbek families are moving away from the old totalitarian society's ideas as depicted in books. New content and important books are being introduced. In this process, the role of the library is not diminishing but rather transforming from a traditional concept to a new one. The educational process for elementary school students is evolving as a spiritual development journey. For this reason, parents and guardians should consider the following when allowing their children to read books:

1. Foster a complex reading process to stimulate the desire to read in elementary school students. This matter indicates their attitude towards libraries. Selecting books should be done carefully because the current level of library culture among elementary school students is not very developed. This is a societal issue, and parental involvement plays a crucial role in solving it. At home, parents should create a conducive environment for their children to read books. Teachers at school should work on developing students' reading habits. In this regard, simple yet challenging books, suitable for the child's maturity level, are the best choice."

2. The spiritual level of the child should be taken into account when choosing a book. The first task of parents in developing reading skills in a child is to help them choose books. The widespread promotion of literature suitable for their level will help children to become worthy citizens of society, mature and complete people of our independent country, and bring benefits to their families and society with their high morale. For this, there should be a spirit of reading in the family.

3. Specialization in book selection. The teacher and parents should follow the path of specialization of the teenager in the process of turning him into a reader. In this regard, it is necessary to abandon the old technology - the idea that specialization is necessary when a child moves to a higher grade.

A reader - the student enriches the life learned in the family with the life events in the book, his understanding of life, human qualities, goodness, values, pride in the life of his descendants, love for the motherland, loyalty to a friend, respect, hard work, and patience will increase. The biggest helper in this regard is fiction. In fiction, any event is expressed through artistic images in an impressive form, in which a young reader can learn many qualities and become a person rich in meaning.

It can be seen from the above considerations that the family is an important and solid foundation in the education of a spiritually mature generation of readers. Therefore, working in harmony with the family in any activity related to the development of reading and improving the culture of reading in the society creates a suitable basis for achieving the intended goals

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